

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO COMMUNICATE WITH THE DEAF SEEKING HEALTHCARE
IN URGENT CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Kevin Foster

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Ayman Tailakh, PhD., RN, Team Leader
Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC, Team Member

May 2024

Author Note

Kevin Foster - <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2022-4066>
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13718101
© 2024 Kevin Foster

ABSTRACT

Deaf and hard of hearing individuals have not attained equal access to healthcare as their hearing counterparts, although the federal government has created laws ensuring equal healthcare accessibility. Inadequate communication between healthcare professionals and the person who is Deaf and hard of hearing offers many hurdles for this population to overcome. With the increased cost of health care and limited Deaf interpreters, communication technology systems have emerged to help bridge the communication gaps. This paper aims to evaluate communication disparities between the Deaf and hard of hearing with their provider in urgent care and to encourage providers in their role as an agent of change. Based on the literature review, this project created and distributed a standard operations protocol, an online pre- and post-survey, a provider interpersonal communication/self-reflection/awareness instrument, and a two-minute video among providers. An overall increase in providers' response was noted, and their eagerness to discuss language barriers was achieved. The results indicated that providers want to work to change the communication disparities between patients who are Deaf or hard of hearing seeking healthcare. Although the sample size was limited, the results were encouraging.

Keywords: Deaf, hard of hearing, communication, video remote interpreter, VRI, American Sign Language

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	VII
BACKGROUND	1
PROBLEM STATEMENT.....	2
PURPOSE STATEMENT	3
SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK.....	3
Peplau’s Interpersonal Relations Theory.....	4
Studies That Used Peplau’s Theory.....	5
Orientation Phase.....	6
Identification Phase.....	8
Exploitation Phase.....	9
Resolution Phase.....	9
Stetler Model of Research Utilization Into Evidence-Based Practice.....	10
Studies That Used the Stetler Model of Research Utilization.....	11
Phase I: Preparation.....	12
Phase II: Validation.....	12
Phase III: Comparative Evaluation.....	13
Phase V: Evaluation.....	15
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	16
Overview.....	16
Methods of Literature Review.....	16
SYNTHESIZING OF THE LITERATURE.....	17
Communication Barriers Faced by the Deaf/HH Patient Seeking Healthcare.....	17
Healthcare Disparities.....	18
Medical Errors Due to Miscommunication.....	19
Language Assistance.....	19

Video Remote Interpreter	20
Health Care Provider Education	21
METHODS	23
Objective	23
Time Frame	23
DESIGN	23
Phase I: Protocol Development and Provider Education	23
Phase II: Implementing VRI	25
Setting	25
Tools	25
PARTICIPANTS AND PROCEDURES	26
Phase I	26
Ethical Consideration	27
Data Collection	27
Data Analysis	27
RESULTS	28
Descriptive Statistics: Participants Characteristics	28
DISCUSSION	36
Recommendations	38
Implications	38
Limitations	39
Conclusion	39
REFERENCES	40
APPENDIX A: MAJOR CONCEPTS OF PEPLAU’S THEORY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS	49
APPENDIX B: PEPLAU’S THEORY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS	50
APPENDIX C: STETLER MODEL OF RESEARCH UTILIZATION	51
APPENDIX D: IRB APPROVAL LETTER	52
APPENDIX E: INSTITUTIONAL APPROVAL LETTER	53
APPENDIX F: PRE-CLINICAL SURVEY	54
APPENDIX G: POST-CLINICAL POST SURVEY	57

APPENDIX H: STANDARD OPERATIONS PROTOCOL	60
APPENDIX I: PROVIDER INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION/SELF- REFLECTION/AWARENESS INSTRUMENT	61
APPENDIX J: STEPS FOR VRI IMPLEMENTATION	62
APPENDIX K: TLC	63
APPENDIX L: PRE-AND POST-SURVEY RESPONSE.....	64
APPENDIX M: RESULTS TABLES.....	65

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

“Hope deferred makes the heart sick: but when the desire comes, it is a tree of life” (Proverbs 13:12). I would like to thank the Lord God of glory for leading me on my journey thus far, “For he that is mighty hath done to me great things; and holy is his name” (Luke 1:49). Ask, and it shall be given you; seek, and you shall find; knock, and it shall be opened unto you (Matthew 7:7).

Thank you, Mom (Henriola), for your wonderfulness, I love you. Thank you, CJ Poindexter, for your friendship. I love you. Thank you, Dr. Wright MD, for your godly friendship with the Lord over 40 years. Thank you, Uncle Clark Culpepper, for your mentorship and insights regarding God and righteousness. Thank you, Deaf Pastor Jack Conley, for your friendship. Thank you, family and friends. Thanks to my DNP group (Karla, Helanie, Dawn, Linda). Thank you, my old friend, Leslie, for your 11th-hour assistance. Thank you, Dr. McClanahan, for your keen insight and direction within the CSUF-DNP program and your concerns for all the students you have been entrusted with.

Finally, thank you, Katie Duong, MPA, for your even-spirited multitasking support of this CSUF-DNP program. You always seem to meet the needs of both faculty and students while putting yourself last. Though most of your deeds have gone unnoticed, you are appreciated!

Background

Hearing loss is a \$980 billion global problem affecting 5% of the world's population (World Health Organization, 2024). In the United States, nearly 3.3% of people 18 years and older have hearing loss (Schoenborn & Heyman, 2008). Approximately 11,552,900 have a hearing disability (Cornell University, n.d.). The incidence of deafness increases with age, from adults to age 45, at 3.1%, rising to 11.1% among adults aged 65 and older. The person who is Deaf and hard of hearing (Deaf/HH) are at risk of not understanding their provider's instructions (Hommes et al., 2018), have compromised health care (Marquete et al., 2019), and are marginalized (Kuenburg et al., 2016). Reducing communication barriers could prevent 671,440 adverse events, with an annual cost savings of \$6.8 billion (Hurtig et al., 2018).

This project aims to highlight the communication disparities between the hearing healthcare providers and the Deaf/HH, ways to improve communication gaps, and encourage providers to self-reflect on their role as change agents.

The upper case “D” identifies the person who is Deaf belonging to a Deaf community, whereas the lower case “d,” hard of hearing person, identifies with the hearing population or with the Deaf community (Bodenmann et al., 2021; Hommes et al., 2018; Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Scheier, 2009). The Deaf/HH are denied equal access, regulated, segregated, and discriminated against with inferior health care access compared to hearing Americans (U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009). Researchers have historically excluded the Deaf/HH who use American Sign Language (ASL) to communicate, creating research disparities and inequalities (McKee et al., 2011). The scarcity of research regarding the Deaf/HH indicates that their needs are not important to the dominant social groups and are unacknowledged (Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Sirch et al., 2017; U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009).

Additionally, there is a risk of communication errors between the Deaf/HH and the hearing provider (Pickens, 2021), vital medical information is excluded (Riedl & Schüßler, 2017), and the Deaf/HH feel vulnerable and lack consonance (Sirch et al., 2017). Providers feel underprepared to treat the Deaf/HH (Abou-Abdallah & Lamyman, 2021) and lack specialized communication skills in caring for the Deaf/HH (Bodenmann et al., 2021). Language barriers are an everyday occurrence between healthcare providers and Deaf/HH (Hommes et al., 2018; Yabe, 2020). Lip reading and written notes are common ineffective communication methods used by providers (Hommes et al., 2018; Kuenburg et al., 2016; Orrie & Motsohi, 2018). The ADA guarantees civil rights protection to citizens with hearing disabilities (U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009). Nevertheless, access to interpreter services is often overlooked by providers (Ebert & Heckerling, 1995). Despite the ADA mandate requiring healthcare settings to provide ASL interpreters, most providers continue to treat the Deaf/HH without an interpreter, using lipreading and note-writing as acceptable forms of communication (Hommes et al., 2018; U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009).

Problem Statement

To bridge the communication disparities between the Deaf/HH and providers, the urgent care providers must conceptualize their role as agents of change to understand the needs of the person who is Deaf/HH. Furthermore, as a substitute for an in-person ASL interpreter, video remote interpreter (VRI) technology offers an alternative to lipreading and note-writing (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020).

Communication between nursing staff and theories is one of the central components in all areas of nursing (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, n.d.).

Effective communication is language concordance. The Deaf/HH seeking treatment in urgent care needs to understand hearing medical personnel, staff, informed consent, treatment, medications, and discharge instructions. Many urgent care settings in Southern California do not have professional ASL interpreters on staff, no Deaf/HH protocols, or VRI technology. Prior to the implementation of VRI, there were no protocols prioritizing interpreters for non-urgent encounters over less urgent ones (Marshall et al., 2019). The patient's opinion matters in healthcare, and healthcare professionals must be sensitive to the patient's preferences and needs (Hommes et al., 2018; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was two-fold. Phase I, create a standard operations protocol (SOP) educating providers on cultivating communication skills with the Deaf/HH, developing and encouraging the provider's role as an agent of change, and using observation, self-reflection, and non-directive listening to bridge the healthcare inequalities experienced by the person who is Deaf/HH. Phase II (post-graduation) implement a VRI program to improve communication gaps between the person who is Deaf/HH and hearing medical professionals in urgent care in Southern California.

Supporting Framework

Theories and frameworks guide clinical practices and projects, organizing change plans (Bonnell & Smith, 2022). Due to the complex needs of the person who is Deaf/HH, there will be one theory (Peplau) and one framework (Stetler) applied to this project. Peplau's interpersonal relations theory focuses on (a) the person who is Deaf/HH as a person with spiritual and physical needs and (b) the relationship with the provider, who must reflect on their inner-self as an agent to foster the most appropriate way to help the patient succeed; this may be as a resource person,

teacher, leader, counselor, surrogate, and or a technical expert (Peplau, 1991). Whereas, Stetler's framework model of research utilization will guide the constructs of the DNP project connecting research evidence into practical building blocks for change in urgent care.

Peplau's Interpersonal Relations Theory

Hildegard Peplau's interpersonal relations theory to improve communication between patients who are Deaf/HH and hearing providers is essential. Language communicates ideas (Walker & Avant, 2018). Peplau's middle-range theory is defined as the process occurring when the professional nurse engages in therapeutic communicative relationships with a patient in need of healthcare through a sequence of four overlapping steps: orientation, identification, exploitation, and resolution (Fernandes et al., 2016; Hagerty et al., 2017).

Peplau's theory originated in 1952 when communication between the nurse and the patient was forbidden (Senn, 2013). The principle of interpersonal relations theory is communication inspired by the provider's willingness to know themselves and exemplify through their actions the highest social and ethical insights (Peplau, 1991). Furthermore, the provider must identify techniques that are compatible with their attitudes and beliefs. Understanding Peplau's theory and connectedness empowers nurses to work through language barriers (Wasaya et al., 2021). The nurse and patient need to communicate to understand a patient's needs.

Peplau was a nurse, educator, and researcher working in a psychiatric ward in the 1940s and 1950s. Peplau participated with the World Health Organization and garnered national and international acclaim (Senn, 2013). There have been 70 years of academic and clinical use of the Peplau model (Appendices A & B) as the theory and framework to introduce evidence into practice; these include clinical practice, research, nursing administration, general nursing

education, and psychiatric nursing curriculums. Peplau's theory will primarily be used in Phase I of this project to lead providers through an inner exploration/self-reflection of themselves to better connect with the patient who is Deaf/HH through an interpersonal relationship-building process and as an agent of change.

Studies That Used Peplau's Theory

The Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS), supported by conceptualized items, surveyed 12,436 patients to investigate the contributions of nursing concerning hospitalized patients' experience. They found Peplau's interpersonal relations theory was an excellent fit for the Institute of Medicine (IOM) conceptual model's latent factor structure (Hagerty et al., 2017). The HCAHPS domains include patients' needs, preferences, values, and physical and emotional support. Peplau's theory emphasizes communication, the nurse-patient relationship, and how those experiences affect the nurse and patients' outcomes.

Recruiting and retaining research participants is a challenge. Penckofer et al. (2011) applied Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations as the framework to study nurse-patient relationships and the recruitment and retention of female participants with type 2 diabetes. The researchers successfully recruited and retained participants through Peplau's framework through thoughtful communication skills, trust, encouragement, and understanding of the individual needs of the patients.

Nursing history fosters viewing patients as a whole with non-segmentation of psychological and physiological (mind, body, and spiritual) needs (Deane & Fain, 2016). The researchers used Peplau's interpersonal relations theory as a framework to assist nursing students in understanding holistic communication skills with older adult patients. Peplau's theory as a

holistic paradigm framework has been used to structure classrooms, laboratory presentations, and conferences.

Orientation Phase

The first step of Peplau's interpersonal relations model is the orientation phase when the nurse and patient meet. This phase explores the interactions between an ill patient and a nurse coming together to communicate and resolve a felt need regarding the patient's health (Peplau, 1991). During the initial communication orientation, the nurse greets the patient and family by name and professional title and, through effective communication, defines the problem to be solved with the guidance of the nurse (Deane & Fain, 2016; Fernandes et al., 2016).

Seeking assistance for a felt need is an essential aspect of the orientation phase and makes a significant difference in the outcome of the patient's personality expansion. The nurse assists the patient in reaching optimal health by considering the educational needs of the patient. Suppose the relationship of the event itself to the personal social growth of the patient is given primary emphasis; in that case, there is a greater chance of the corporate healthcare team solving the patient's problem (Peplau, 1991). The orientation phase establishes patient comfort through the initial relationship, and a consensus is reached regarding treatment. The progression of the orientation phase elicits more questions from the patient, and the nurse assists the patient to a comfort level while helping them better understand their concerns (Deane & Fain, 2016).

The nurse conveys an interest concerning the patient's needs, holistic assessments, and gathering data while setting an interactive tone (Peplau, 1991). As the orientation phase progresses, the patient is encouraged to ask questions. The nurse's response helps the patient feel secure within their interactions, and trust is built. However, patients with a communication barrier are three times more likely to experience dissatisfaction and preventable adverse events

that may lead to poorer patient outcomes, suffering, and longer hospital stays (Hurtig et al., 2018).

During the orientation phase as well as the remaining three phases, the nurse may function in a series of overlapping roles:

1. Stranger, the initial meeting of the patient and family (Peplau, 1991).
2. Resource person, giving specific needed information (Peplau, 1991).
3. Teacher, problem-solving approach to patient's needs (Peplau, 1991).
4. Leader, gathering evidence and providing guidance (Peplau, 1991).
5. Counselor, observe and listen to the patient and assist in identifying and formulating feelings regarding the disease process (Peplau, 1991; Wasaya et al., 2021).
6. Surrogate, the patient casts the nurse as a surrogate and shares feelings from prior relationships (Peplau, 1991).
7. Technical expert, understanding the professional medical devices as applied to patient care (Fernandes et al., 2016; Peplau, 1991).

Creating a comfortable setting in urgent care where the patient who is Deaf/HH communicates thoughts, concerns, and questions is lacking due to the communication barriers. Communication barriers contribute to health disparities between healthcare providers and patients who are Deaf/HH (Hommes et al., 2018). The patient needs assistance planning the use of services a professional organization can offer (Peplau, 1991). To demonstrate sincerity, respect, and honesty in communication is to understand a patient's needs and recognize their personal feelings, emotions, sensitivity, and dignity (Broca & de Ferreira, 2018). The need for urgent care to gather essential information on the patient's medical, surgical, mental, family,

social, spiritual, and allergy history is an essential process that ultimately dictates the patient's outcomes.

Identification Phase

The identification phase is defined as the patient's initial impression beginning to be clarified and the understanding of what the healthcare team can offer in response to the patient's needs (Peplau, 1991). When the provider creates a safe place, the patient can communicate their feelings while receiving the care needed and undertake their illness as an experience that reorients feelings and strengthens positive forces in their personality. The patient responds to the person who best meets their immediate needs, and both collectively decide on a provider and a plan of care (Fernandes et al., 2016). Nursing is an interrelated function, a maturing force, and the providers must be aware of their feelings and what they can and ought to be doing (Peplau, 1991).

Illness threatens a person's health, dignity, feelings, and self-worth. However, as the patient's interpersonal relationship grows with the assistance of the nurse professional, the patient is less threatened by their circumstances (Peplau, 1991). Identification makes constructive learning possible through the patient's efforts while becoming less dependent on the nurse. However, the nurse is identified as the basis of service to the patient and is recognized as beneficial.

It is the provider, through an interpersonal relationship with the patient, that fosters a forward movement in the patient's personality that displaces helplessness with empowerment, creativity, and productivity (Peplau, 1991). Open communication is essential to the patient-provider relationship (Riedl & Schüßler, 2017). The urgent care provider must best approach a communication barrier and assist a patient's communication needs (Fernandes et al., 2016).

Lip-reading and note-writing are common ineffective ways providers use to communicate with a person who is Deaf/HH (Hommes et al., 2018; Kuenburg et al., 2016; Orrie & Motschi, 2018). The preferred way of communication for the Deaf/HH is ASL (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019). As a substitute for an in-person ASL interpreter in urgent care, VRI is a better option than lip reading and note writing (Hommes et al., 2018; Lion et al., 2015).

Exploitation Phase

As the patient identifies with the nurse and understands the interpersonal relationship, the patient makes full use of the goods and services offered by the healthcare organization and will exploit them based on self-interest and needs (Peplau, 1991). Exploitation overlaps identification and resolution, the fourth phase of the interpersonal relationship. This phase encompasses prior and future accomplishments by the patient to strike balance between dependency (noticed in the orientation phase) and independence.

The patient who is Deaf/HH comes into urgent care for a medical problem and trusts the skills and professionalism of the provider. During the exploitation phase, the patient may realize personal strength by working through obstacles and exploiting the healthcare system to meet a desire through services available to the patient (Peplau, 1991). If a patient who is Deaf/HH requests an ASL interpreter through the use of VRI service to meet their preferred communication needs, that demonstrates an area of the patient's growth.

Resolution Phase

The resolution is the fourth and final phase of the interpersonal relationship. The patient willingly adopts new goals formulated during exploring and exploitation (Peplau, 1991). Resolution infers that the patient is gradually freeing themselves from the identification phase and can stand alone with the teachings of the nurse and the independence of their newfound

strength, free from dependency to more productive social activities and relationships. This phase is preparation for discharge by reviewing accomplishments, teachings, medication instructions-reconciliation, and keeping follow-up appointments with their primary care provider (Deane & Fain, 2016). The patient is now independent, the medical or surgical needs are fulfilled, and the nurse-patient joint efforts are dissolved (Fernandes et al., 2016). Southern California urgent cares must position themselves to meet the communication needs of every patient who is Deaf/HH desiring health care. Employing VRI in urgent care and educating providers will bridge the communication gaps between Deaf/HH and hearing providers.

Peplau's theory teaches providers to know themselves by exploring their feelings through self-reflection to develop and understand the interpersonal relationship with the patient they are serving and to enhance their clinical skills as agents of change (Peplau, 1991). Without effective communication, relationships cannot grow. Communication barriers have historically plagued the person who is Deaf/HH creating vast gaps and unequal treatment in the Deaf/HH's culturally rich community (Kuenburg et al., 2016; Marquete et al., 2019).

Equal access to quality and effective healthcare has been a perpetual struggle for the person who is Deaf/HH (McKee et al., 2011). However, VRI offers the person who is Deaf/HH a critical tool to bridge the communication gaps with hearing medical professionals.

Communicating effectively with patients decreases disparities, miscommunications, and preventable medication errors while improving patient outcomes (Hurtig et al., 2018).

Stetler Model of Research Utilization Into Evidence-Based Practice

Evaluating the suitability of a framework is necessary to complement a clinical project (Bonnell & Smith, 2022). The use of Stetler's framework is an excellent choice to guide this DNP

project. A framework is defined as the appropriateness, desirability, feasibility, and manner of using research findings in an individual's or group's practice (Stetler, 2001).

Cheryl Stetler's model of research utilization helps the advanced practice nurse (APN) apply critical thinking and reflective practice to create formal change within an organization (Appendix C), how to approach the relationship between research use and evidence-based practice (EBP), and how to apply research findings into practice (National Collaborating Centre for Methods and Tools, n.d.). The model was developed in 1994 to facilitate empirical research findings and was revived in 2001 (White, 2019). The model is individually driven towards the practitioner, promoting internal data (personal experience/beliefs, quality improvement) and external evidence (primary search of evidence and organization). The model describes five phases of research, (I) preparation, (II) validation, (III) comparative evaluation, (IV) translation/application, and (V) evaluation.

Studies That Used the Stetler Model of Research Utilization

Job satisfaction is a significant characteristic needed to retain good nurses (Romp & Kiehl, 2009). A nurse educator hires approximately 150 new registered nurses yearly at an urban community medical center and determines a need to evaluate their preceptor program for new hires. Stetler's model of research utilization was selected as a framework to help develop staff educators in the appropriate application of existing research. Accurately applying Stetler's model helped determine whether the literature supports the development of preceptors to improve nurse retention. After the implementation of this program, the 12-month nurse turnover dropped from 13.9% to 3.9%, an estimated savings of \$1.8 million.

Traditionally, women do not perceive themselves at risk for heart attacks as men (Lefler, 2005). However, more women die earlier without preventative lifesaving measures for acute

myocardial infarctions (AMI) than men due to their delays in seeking treatment. Stetler's research model of utilization to synthesize nursing literature centering on why older women delay seeking treatment for AMI and the proposed APN interventions to reduce this prehospital time interval was used to guide the literature review. The most significant reason for delays revealed in the literature was the incorrect interpretation of AMI and behavior response regarding treatment. The literature also encourages APNs to provide education opportunities and teaching with brochures to change the at-risk woman's knowledge of AMI.

Phase I: Preparation

The purpose of the preparation phase is specific regarding clarity and the significance of internal or external factors (Stetler, 2001). Internal factors such as personal beliefs may diminish objectivity. In comparison, external factors may be organizational goals, deadlines, or political issues that can delay a change agenda. The preparation phase directs the urgent care provider to be conscious during the literature review and consider the patient's specific needs and stakeholders' demands. Knowing that effective communication improves patient outcomes in urgent care helps identify appropriate and relevant research literature suitable for this DNP project.

Phase II: Validation

The validation phase appraises the relevant findings of the study, not necessarily the study (White, 2019). This phase centers on the APN's pragmatic approach, where there is a need to reflect on studies and variables and how they can be practically applied to daily activities in the urgent care setting (Stetler, 2001). The model helps practitioners assess research and EBP findings and how to apply them in practice.

The two types of research knowledge (products of research and the research process) are incorporated into the Stetler model (Stetler, 2001). Using research products is using research findings with validated instruments of measurement. The evidence specific to urgent care needs and identifying variables that can be applied will guide the practice needs of urgent care. Critical thinking will be essential in transforming research knowledge into practice.

Phase III: Comparative Evaluation

Synthesizing literature takes the best evidence and makes it readily available to the nursing professional (Bonnell & Smith, 2022). Although a nurse expert specializing in an area of practice can use a single research study, multiple studies were used, reviewed, and synthesized. Organizing, condensing, and gaining synthesized meaning occurs with comparative evaluation (Stetler, 2001).

Formulating a practical approach is imminent (Stetler, 2001). This can be an individual practitioner or a collective group of interprofessional. Evaluate the feasibility of the proposed change by reviewing the risks, resources, and readiness to fit VRI and providers' education into urgent care practice.

The comparative evaluations consist of four applicability criteria for the synthesizing of studies.

1. Substantiating evidence relevant to change in practice as guidelines or professional standards (Lefler, 2005; White, 2019). The U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division (2020) issued revised regulations for the ADA Title II (state and local government services) and Title III (public accommodations and commercial facilities) to ensure a person with a disability can effectively communicate as with people without a

disability. VRI is an aid and service offered to the person who is Deaf/HH, and the following standards must be met:

- a. Real-time, full-motion high-quality video, and audio over a dedicated high-speed, wide-bandwidth connection or wireless connection delivering video images that do not produce lags, grainy images, choppy, blurry, or irregular pauses in communication.
 - b. A large, sharply allocated image of the ASL interpreter's face, arms, hands, fingers, and the person who is Deaf/HH face, arms, hands, and fingers using sign language, regardless of his or her body position.
 - c. Clear, audible transmission of voices.
 - d. Adequate training of staff to ensure proper quick set-up and operation.
2. Current practice is a time to consider whether the researched theories can provide the evidence to effectively change how urgent care provides healthcare services to the person who is Deaf/HH (Lefler, 2005).
 3. Fit substantiates findings in the research with a specific use in the clinical setting (Stetler, 2001).
 4. Feasibility assesses the risks and benefits of the desired change (Stetler, 2001).

Systematic literature reviews are highly recommended, where users identify, organize, and condense information across multiple studies to facilitate a change in practice. Although evidence is the goal, supplemental findings may be identified to meet a desired need.

In many ways, urgent care has filled gaps for patients who cannot be seen by their primary care physicians and has improved access to care (Villaseñor & Krouse, 2016). Insufficient communication and knowledge on how to navigate through the healthcare system presents

problems for the person who is Deaf/HH. However, effective communication will ensure the quality of care in urgent care.

Phase IV: Translation/Application

The translation/application phase focuses on how to implement synthesized findings and recommendations into practice (Stetler, 2001). It is deciding who should do what, when, and how with the evidence; there may or may not have detailed guidelines, policies, and procedures, and providers may have to have a consensus regarding theoretical information and their expert judgment on how to proceed. At this point, the development of plans for formal organizational change will occur. Plans should reflect translating reviewed research into practice and the dissemination of findings through urgent care.

Phase V: Evaluation

Evaluation is the final phase, when practical information is observed through formal or informal measures or tests for the feasibility of change (Stetler, 2001). These findings will determine whether the organizational change is acceptable and can be extended to other urgent care settings or whether changes need modification or be rejected. The decision to formally integrate VRI routinely in urgent care and shun handwriting and lip reading will improve communication and patient care for Southern California's Deaf/HH community. If there is a delay in connectivity with Wi-Fi or bandwidth, that could decrease patient satisfaction. As a precautionary measure, optimal internet connections will ensure ideal VRI functioning. Routine evaluation and refinement of the equipment must occur to ensure the change has achieved the goals of urgent care.

Review of Literature

Overview

This literature review provides scientific support and is essential for understanding the clinical topic and interventions used to address a clinical problem in urgent care. A literature review must be timely, relevant research. Evaluating literature is significant for addressing gaps in urgent care and will help gain knowledge regarding a proposed change plan.

Methods of Literature Review

The literature review was conducted using CINAHL, PubMed, Cochrane, and Medline. The keywords used were Deaf, hard of hearing, communication technology, VRI, and sign language. The CINAHL database was used for the more significant number of search strategies. Limits consisted of advanced search, mostly peer-reviewed, abstract, and full text, without publication dates due to the scarcity of research regarding the Deaf/HH and VRI. Keyword Deaf yielded 1,163. Deaf communication produced 26 results. Deaf communication and healthcare offered 67 results. Deaf, hard of hearing, and communication gave 500 results. Deaf technology and communication returned 51 results. A revision of the search using communication technology and health yielded 337 results. Communication, ASL, and health offered 21 results. CINAHL search using VRI yielded 194 results, and VRI and Deaf returned 65. Citation chaining was performed on references in the articles identified. The inclusion criteria were articles written in English. The exclusion criteria were opinion pieces.

The literature review was divided into six subsections, (1) Communication Barriers Faced by the Deaf/HH Patient Seeking Healthcare, (2) Healthcare Disparities, (3) Medical Errors Due to Miscommunication, (4) Language Assistance, (5) VRI, and (6) Health Care Provider

Education. Stetler's research utilization model will be used to review the literature and critically process the EBP and how they best fit the current urgent care setting.

Synthesizing of the Literature

Communication Barriers Faced by the Deaf/HH Patient Seeking Healthcare

Nursing concepts are understood and communicated through language (American Organization of Nurse Executives [AONE], 2015). Communication barriers decrease the quality of healthcare (Yabe, 2020). Communication barriers are the most significant issue for patients who are Deaf/HH that continue to have difficulty accessing quality and effective healthcare (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020); as a result, the ADA has provided legal protection (U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009). However, 27 years after the passage of the ADA, providers continue to rely on lipreading and written notes for communication with the person who is Deaf/HH despite the ADA requirements of reasonable communication accommodations (Hommes et al., 2018).

Poor communication between the provider in urgent care and the patient who is Deaf/HH sends a nonverbal message of unimportance (Riedl & Schüßler, 2017). Emphasizing communication between the provider and patient is paramount for patient-centered care and is a fundamental component of a positive impact on patient satisfaction (Jardien-Baboo et al., 2016; Levinson et al., 2010; Robinson et al., 2008). Increasing personal awareness among healthcare providers regarding communicating with Deaf/HH improves their understanding of themselves and the Deaf culture, provides skills for providers, and improves healthcare equity (Morisod et al., 2022).

The quality of care administered by providers to the person who is Deaf/HH is antiquated. Language barriers create adverse consequences for health and health care (Marshall

et al., 2019). Providers need to understand a patient who is Deaf/HH using ASL to communicate struggles with the use of the English language (Yabe, 2020). The Deaf/HH accurately interpret only 20 to 30% of the English language and prefer ASL to English, which is regarded as a second language (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019). Since ASL is a visual language, providers and ancillary staff must give their full attention to the Deaf/HH because talking and inessential patient engagement activities do not work well in this culture (Hommes et al., 2018). The uniqueness of ASL interpreters helps bridge the communication gaps and decrease healthcare disparities between the Deaf/HH and healthcare providers (Hommes et al., 2018).

Healthcare Disparities

Healthcare disparities are barriers between the Deaf/HH and their provider (Hommes et al., 2018). There is an extensively documented lack of understanding of the patient who are Deaf/HH and their culture regarding healthcare (Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Sirch et al., 2017; U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009). Research methods relying on written and spoken languages historically exclude patients who are Deaf/HH and who lack familiarity with spoken languages (McKee et al., 2011; Napier et al., 2018). The Deaf/HH have increased difficulties accessing quality healthcare, mainly due to their reliance on ASL as a preferred language over English (Kushalnagar et al., 2019). Most Deaf/HH do not understand providers' diagnoses, health teaching, medication education, or discharge instructions (Hommes et al., 2018). Language barriers decrease the quality of healthcare (Hommes et al., 2018; Yabe, 2020). Obtaining equitable health care remains problematic for the Deaf/HH post-ADA (Kushalnagar et al., 2019).

The Deaf/HH continue to experience healthcare barriers primarily attributed to a lack of understanding by providers (Kuenburg et al., 2016). Half of the Deaf/HH do not understand their providers' discharge instructions, and 81% of providers failed to use the teach-back method to reinforce patient understanding (Hommes et al., 2018). The ADA aims to eliminate discrimination against disabled individuals and mandate equal access to health care services (U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009).

Medical Errors Due to Miscommunication

Reducing communication barriers prevents adverse events, with an estimated annual savings of \$6.8 billion (Hurtig et al., 2018). Errors and misrepresentations can occur with ad hoc interpreters (Flores, 2005). Professional interpreters make fewer errors of potential consequences than ad hoc or no interpreters (Flores, 2005; Flores et al., 2012). Medical errors dropped significantly with the number of professional training hours greater than 100, versus interpreters with less than 100 hours of service training (Flores et al., 2012).

Lower interpretation errors and improved patient comprehension increase adherence to follow-up appointments and treatments, improving health outcomes (Karliner et al., 2007). Using trained medical interpreters increases patient satisfaction, office visits, and prescriptions. In contrast, when there is no interpreter or an ad hoc interpreter, there is an increase in medical tests, hospitalizations, and health costs. Important determinants that influence medication error are lack of communication, poor work environment, excessive work pressure, interruptions, and a misunderstanding of what constitutes an error (Gracia et al., 2019).

Language Assistance

There is a failure to provide language assistance to patients with limited English proficiency (LEP; Flores et al., 2012). Many patients do not receive professional medical

interpretation and resort to using ad hoc interpreters, such as family members, friends, or having no interpreter (Flores et al., 2012). Themes surrounding the Deaf/HH seeking healthcare are (a) vulnerability, (b) the need for reciprocal understanding and sensitivity, (c) lack of consonance between need and care, and (d) a sense of a lack of empowerment (Sirch et al., 2017). Southern California is multinational, multicultural, and multilingual and has adapted to the diverse healthcare needs of most of its inhabitants; yet, there remain challenges to accommodate a patient who is Deaf/HH with language diversities (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). Because of communication barriers and health inequalities among the Deaf/HH, language assistance must be offered without cost to the patient (Marshall et al., 2019).

Video Remote Interpreter

Three standard language communication assistance methods used in the healthcare setting are (1) in-person interpreting, (2) over-the-phone interpreting, and (3) VRI (Marshall et al., 2019). VRI was spawned by assistive technology (Kushalnagar et al., 2019). The VRI assists the patient who is Deaf/HH without an in-person professional ASL interpreter. VRI technology bridges the communication gaps between the people who are Deaf/HH and hearing providers. Using VRI technology for patients with LEP had greater diagnosis comprehension, effective communication, and improved patient-provider rapport (Lion et al., 2015).

Providers expressed improved patient communication and relationships using VRI and preferred VRI in non-urgent situations (Yabe, 2020). Before the implementation of VRI in a Southern California hospital, no protocols were prioritizing critical interpreting service encounters over less urgent encounters (Marshall et al., 2019), and there was a substantial decrease in the use of VRI, mainly due to connectivity problems; nevertheless, when the

problems were fixed, the use of VRI increased. Providers had positive feedback when using VRI as a convenient, speedy way to communicate with a person who is Deaf/HH when an in-person interpreter was unavailable. However, some providers had negative experiences with VRI, such as technical issues (Yabe, 2020). Training for using VRI among providers and improving equipment with better connectivity is recommended to increase health equality while decreasing potential medical errors due to misunderstandings.

Health Care Provider Education

The lack of healthcare understanding of the Deaf culture has been acknowledged in literature (Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Sirch et al., 2017; U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division, 2009). Provider training is valuable for improving patient-centeredness communication and increasing a provider's communication skills (Helitzer et al., 2011). An essential part of the professional nurse leader's maintenance of competence is lifelong learning (Babenko et al., 2017). Visualizing what is going on in the patient is a skill developed (Peplau, 1991). It is a necessity for providers to be educated in the latest tools available to assist in improving healthcare outcomes in urgent care. The provider must be able to interpret the patient's primary concerns. This act is a learned skill developed through education, patience, observation, and experience. Huddles involving staff improve the accountability of clinical issues, problem-solving, and teamwork communication while refining collaboration; the positive impact of huddles can extend beyond processes to include advances in urgent care clinical outcomes (Lin et al., 2022; Mena Lora et al., 2020; Pimentel et al., 2021).

For successful communication and implementation of VRI, providers must be educated (Peplau, 1991). A caring culture can be achieved through the education of providers regarding effective communication and understanding their thoughts, feelings, and emotions, which will

aid in providing patient-centered care for a person who is Deaf (Broca & de Ferreira, 2018; Hommes et al., 2018; Jardien-Baboo et al., 2016). The value of a team willing to effectively communicate with the patient and each other develops a caring culture within an urgent care setting.

Methods

Objective

Based on the review of literature, this DNP project created and distributed a standard operations protocol (SOP), an online pre- and post-survey, a provider interpersonal communication/self-reflection/awareness instrument and a two-minute VRI video demonstrating the use of technology to improve communication with the patient who is Deaf/HH. The purpose was to improve providers' communication, knowledge and confidence as an agent of change, using observation, self-reflection, and non-directive listening while treating the person who is Deaf/HH. Non-directive listening is listening to someone's problems to help counsel and educate them that they will make their own decisions (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.). The unprepared provider (Abou-Abdallah & Lamyman, 2021) needs more specialized communication skills (Bodenmann et al., 2021) to transform ideas learned in the past that have been known to cause a provider to practice uncritically (Peplau, 1991).

Time Frame

The timeframe began December 2023 through April 2024. The data were collected in March 2024. In spring 2024, the data analysis was performed, followed by the project discussion. The lead author met with providers and subsequently emailed surveys. Phase II of this project, post-graduation, will involve the implementation of a VRI.

Design

Phase I: Protocol Development and Provider Education

A SOP was developed to educate the providers to know themselves as agent of change as well as understand the use of VRI to improve communication with the person who is Deaf/HH in urgent care. The pre-and post-surveys were taken individually at the providers' convenience.

Providers were encouraged to take the post-survey immediately after the pre-survey and watch the video.

These strategies assisted in framing effective personal growth, self-reflection, and redirecting the provider's feelings while learning a non-directive approach in practice (Peplau, 1991; Rogers et al., 2014; Winkel et al., 2017). This project used Peplau's interpersonal relation theory to educate the providers on the importance of understanding themselves and the patient, internally and professionally. A provider's reflections enhance learning, deepening empathy and professionalism (Winkel et al., 2017). Furthermore, ideas and principles guide practices when open to review and reconstruction (Peplau, 1991) while bridging the communication gaps and disparities of the person who is Deaf/HH.

In addition, the steps in Stettler's framework offered a practical approach for the preparation, validation, comparison, application, and evaluation to develop this DNP project (Stetler, 2001). Stetler's model guides research findings to individual patients, cultures, providers, or other targets through a critical-thinking process. Without critical thinking, research findings can become thoughtless and lead to inappropriate changes in practice.

The provider must gain essential information regarding the provider's feelings, attitudes, observation skills, and healthcare knowledge (Hagerty et al., 2017; Peplau, 1991). However, these skills require exclusive devotion and preparation (American Association of Critical-Care Nurses, 2019), with a keen attentiveness to a patient's concerns (Hagerty et al., 2017).

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from California State University, Los Angeles, and approval from the lead author's institution was secured prior to the start of this project (Appendices D & E).

Phase II: Implementing VRI

Post-graduation, phase II will evaluate patient outcomes relating to providers' knowledge and implementation of VRI. This project phase will continue to build on Stetler's model of research utilization into evidence-based practice. VRI technology enables providers to deliver effective quality assistant language technology to the person who is Deaf/HH in the absence of an in-person professional ASL interpreter (Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). Effective communication with providers improves patient satisfaction and quality patient outcomes (Fossli et al., 2011; Gabrielsen et al., 2016; Hommes et al., 2018; McKee et al., 2011; Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Reeves & Kokoruwe, 2005; Riedl & Schüßler, 2017; Sirch et al., 2017). VRI technology will allow providers to apply Peplau's interpersonal relationship theory through effective communication. Thus bridging the communication gaps, creating patient-provider competencies, mutual respect, and understanding desired needs.

Setting

This project was implemented at two urgent care centers in Southern California. Urgent care offers a wide range of services. It delivers medical evaluations, care, treatment, and teaching regarding injuries and illnesses that are not life-threatening and do not need immediate care from a hospital-based treatment center or an emergency department (ED). Urgent care is an alternative choice between hospitals or EDs. The urgent care is open seven days a week, 12-hour shifts, with one provider per shift. Five ancillary staff members with medical assistance support the daily operations of urgent care.

Tools

Measuring providers' communication, knowledge, confidence, observation/self-reflection/non-directive listening skills helped understand gaps when providers treat and

communicate with the patient who is Deaf/HH. The survey used was a 20-item instrument and a six-point Likert scale with responses from (1) not at all, (2) slightly, (3) somewhat, (4) mostly, (5) very much, and (6) yes and no. The clinical provider pre- and post-survey (Appendices F & G) questions concerned the frequency of providers treating a patient who is Deaf/HH, how comfortable they are providing care, the use of VRI, non-directive listening, and self-reflection. A provider SOP for improving communication with the Deaf/HH (Appendix H) and a provider interpersonal communication/self-reflection/awareness instrument were used to improve patient interpersonal communication, provider self-reflection, awareness, and knowledge (Appendix I). Post-graduation, defining the necessary steps for VRI implementation will be used (Appendix J); furthermore, an acronym was created to help staff demonstrate care and compassion regarding the unique needs of the Deaf/HH and to utilize VRI resources. “TLC” means “tender loving care” or, in this case, “turn on language to communicate.” TLC graphics will be posted on the VRI tablets (Appendix K).

Participants and Procedures

Phase I

There were 14 participants for this project, including the lead author in phase I. The participants were contacted directly by the lead author. A description of the DNP project, the goals, and the project was discussed. Confidentiality was ensured, and providers agreed to participate in the project and gave consent by taking part in the survey. The SOP and the surveys were reviewed and emailed. It is imperative to have providers in the urgent care setting familiar with the diversity of medical conditions in a fast-paced environment with a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic patient population in Southern California.

Ethical Consideration

The principal investigator completed Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI) training. A letter of approval was signed and received from the CEO of urgent care. The project contains minimal risk to participants, including losing confidentiality or coercion. The perceived risks can be alleviated by replacing providers' identifiers with documentation numbers. Providers' scheduling, responsibilities, and opportunities to advance professionally within urgent care would not be affected by their refusal to participate or withdraw from the project. No identifiable provider or patient information was gathered for this project. Potential data will be deidentified and stored on an Excel spreadsheet on a laptop that remains locked in the lead author's office when not in use. The laptop is password-protected. Only the lead author has the password and access to the laptop.

Data Collection

Data were collected at several periods, starting with the pre-survey, followed by the SOP, provider interpersonal communication/self-reflection/awareness instrument, the two-minute VRI educational video, and the post-survey. The demographic information collected from participating providers included current work title, time in practice, education level, age, gender, language/ languages spoken, and knowledge regarding Deaf culture.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Qualtrics™ Software for providers' changes in knowledge and attitudes regarding the patient who is Deaf/HH. There was no identifiable information attached to any of the study participants. Data will be safeguarded for three years after the completion of the DNP project in a locked drawer in the principal investigator's office.

Results

After watching the VRI technology video, providers' confidence improved to 9.9%, providers' comfort levels improved to 32.42%, recognizing providers' position as an agent of change improved to 25.26%, willingness to discuss language barriers improved to 40.66%, eagerness to treat Deaf/HH increased to 41.8%, willingness to use VRI improved 1.65% and non-directive listening improved 47.8% (Appendix L).

Descriptive Statistics: Participants Characteristics

A total of 14 full-time and part-time urgent care healthcare providers participated in this doctoral project. The group included eight men and six women, with 12 of them being physician assistants (PAs) and the remaining two nurse practitioners (NPs). Additionally, 58.33% of participants held master's degrees. In terms of experience, 66.67% had been in the healthcare industry for 20 years or more, and 75% were fluent in English. The answers to the questions may vary if participants fail to answer any of the questions. If one participant did not answer a question, the number would decrease to 13. However, if two participants missed answering a question, the total number of participants may decrease to 12. These descriptive statistics are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1*Demographic Characteristics of Providers*

Variable	Testing time	
	Pretest	Posttest
Gender		
Female	6 (46.15%)	6 (46.15%)
Male	7 (53.85%)	7 (53.85%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	13 (100.00%)
License practice		
PA	11 (84.62%)	11 (84.62%)
NP	2 (15.38%)	2 (15.38%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	13 (100.00%)
Years health experience		
6-10	2 (15.38%)	2 (16.67%)
11-15	1 (7.69%)	1 (8.33%)
16-20	1 (7.69%)	1 (8.33%)
more than 20	9 (69.23%)	8 (66.67%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)
Highest education		
Bachelor's	4 (33.33%)	4 (33.33%)
Master's	7 (58.33%)	7 (58.33%)
Doctoral	1 (8.33%)	1 (8.33%)
Total	12 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)
Fluent languages		
English	9 (81.82%)	9 (75.00%)
Armenian	1 (9.09%)	2 (16.67%)
Other	1 (9.09%)	1 (8.33%)
Total	11 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not sum to 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.

Baseline data collected preceding the VRI technology video demonstration indicated that around 53.84% (Table 2) of urgent care providers were moderately comfortable with treating

Deaf/HH individuals, though only 61.53% felt confident in doing so. Before viewing the VRI technology video, 76.92% of providers had not used this type of technology (Table 2). Moreover, 69.23% seldom addressed language barriers (Table 2), which limited the Deaf/HH chances for successful communication in an urgent care context. Of the Deaf/HH patients visiting urgent care, 92.31% were male, 61.53% used lip-reading, and the majority were accompanied by a hearing family member (Table 2).

Table 2

Baseline Provider Perspectives, Practices, and Deaf/HH Demographics

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
How comfortable do you feel rendering care for a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	5	38.46
Somewhat	2	15.38
Mostly	2	15.38
Very Much	4	30.77
How often do you discuss language barriers among providers when considering a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?		
Not at all	2	15.38
Slightly	7	53.85
Somewhat	3	23.08
Mostly	1	7.69
How confident do you feel in treating a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	3	23.08
Somewhat	2	15.38
Mostly	2	15.38
Very Much	6	46.15
How often do you treat a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Slightly	10	76.92

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	1	7.69
How often do you educate a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Not at all	2	15.38
Slightly	8	61.54
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	1	7.69
Very Much	1	7.69
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care accompanied by a hearing family member or friend?		
Yes	12	92.31
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily female?		
Yes	5	38.46
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily male?		
Yes	3	23.08
Do the Deaf who seek urgent care read lips?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Slightly	2	15.38
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	8	61.54
Very Much	1	7.69
Have you used video remote interpreter VRI technology?		
Yes	3	23.08

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Self-reflection among providers increased from 61.54% (Table 3) to 64.29% (Table 4).

Providers' non-directive listening skills increased after watching the VRI technology video from 30.77% (Table 3) to 78.57% (Table 4).

Table 3*Provider Confidence and Reflective Practices*

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Do you think your confidence level treating the Deaf or hard-of-hearing will increase after using video remote interpreter VRI technology?		
Somewhat	2	15.38
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	3	23.08
Very Much	7	53.85
How often do you engage in self-reflection as a provider in your practice?		
Somewhat	4	30.77
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	4	30.77
Very Much	4	30.77
How often do you utilize non-directive listening?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Somewhat	5	38.46
Slightly	3	23.08
Mostly	1	7.69
Very Much	3	23.08
How often do you reflect on your professional calling/role as an agent of change?		
Somewhat	6	46.15
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	3	23.08
Very Much	3	23.08

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not sum to 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.

Providers comfortability levels were enhanced from 46.15% (Table 2) to 78.57% (Table 4) after watching the VRI technology video. Providers confidence level regarding treating Deaf/HH patients improved after watching the VRI technology video from 61.53% (Table 2) to

71.43% (Table 4). Providers' willingness to discuss language barriers improved from 69.23% (Table 2) to 71.43% (Table 4) after watching the VRI technology video. Providers eagerness to treat more patients who are Deaf/HH increased after watching the VRI technology video, from 15.35% (Table 2) to 57.15% (Table 4). Finally, providers had a clearer insight into their professional mission as advocates for positive change after watching the VRI technology video; understanding increased from 46.16% (Table 3) to 71.42% (Table 4).

Table 4

Impact of VRI Training Video on Healthcare Providers' Confidence and Practices with Deaf/HH

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
After watching the VRI Video, how comfortable do you feel rendering care for a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	5	35.71
Very Much	6	42.86
After watching the VRI Video, will you discuss language barriers among providers when considering a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	2	14.29
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
Has your confidence level in treating a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing improved after watching the video?		
Not at all	1	7.14
Slightly	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
Do you think you will treat more patients who are Deaf and hard-of-hearing after watching the video?		

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Slightly	3	21.43
Somewhat	3	21.43
Mostly	2	14.29
Very Much	6	42.86
Do you think you are better equipped to educate patients who are Deaf and hard-of-hearing after watching the video?		
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	4	28.57
Very Much	8	57.14
Will you self-reflect more often after watching the video?		
Somewhat	5	35.71
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	6	42.86
Will your non-directive listening increase after watching this video?		
Somewhat	3	21.43
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	8	57.14
After viewing this video, do you have a clearer insight into your professional mission as an advocate for positive change?		
Somewhat	4	28.57
Mostly	5	35.71
Very Much	5	35.71
After watching the video, do you believe that your education as an NP, PA, MD, or DO aids in treating Deaf or hard-of-hearing patients?"		
Somewhat	4	28.57
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
After watching the video, do you feel that your experience equips you to effectively use VRI technology in treating Deaf or hard-of-hearing patients?		
Not at all	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	4	28.57
Very Much	7	50.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.

Discussion

Ill-equipped providers attempting to communicate with the patient who is Deaf/HH seeking urgent care have plagued the Deaf/HH community, marginalizing their quality of care (Hommes et al., 2018; Kuenburg et al., 2016). Poor communication is linked to poor quality of care (Hommes et al., 2018; Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). The findings of this DNP project utilizing the VRI video to educate providers regarding VRI technology and encouraging the use thereof demonstrated a positive impact on providers who have used this technology and, more importantly, on those who have not. The results correlate with research articles that have validated the improved communication that occurs when providers utilize the VRI technology in treating Deaf/HH patients (Lion et al., 2015; Yabe, 2020). It is associated with improved confidence and comfortability among providers communicating and treating the person who is Deaf/HH, which will decrease communication barriers while increasing patient satisfaction and patient outcomes (Fossli et al., 2011; Gabrielsen et al., 2016; Hommes et al., 2018; McKee et al., 2011; Orrie & Motsohi, 2018; Reeves & Kokoruwe, 2005; Riedl & Schüßler, 2017; Sirch et al., 2017).

At a Southern California hospital, in-person interpreting services were the most utilized communication method, accounting for 64.0% of the total interpreting minutes (Marshall et al., 2019). Following the implementation of VRI, the use of over-the-phone interpreter services fell to 26.0%, marking a 37.5% decrease, while VRI usage increased to 10% of the overall interpreting minutes. Among the 64 languages frequently encountered at the hospital, VRI technology has proven to be an effective tool in bridging language barriers, with ASL interpreting emerging as the third most common language service provided.

Furthermore, VRI has been highlighted for its flexibility, efficiency, and accessibility, offering a significant advantage over traditional in-person interpretation methods (Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). In consonance with the clinical problem, this work examined providers' confidence levels, comfortability, willingness to discuss language barriers, eagerness to treat Deaf/HH, non-directive listening skills, and being an agent of change, all surrounding the healthcare treatment of the Deaf/HH. This DNP project found that the above variables increased after watching the VRI technology video. More specifically, non-directive listening skills and providers' recognition of themselves as agents of change improved after reviewing the provider interpersonal communication/self-reflection/awareness instrument and the SOP. These results met the expectations of the lead author.

In the discussion of our quality improvement initiative, our study's results resonate well with existing literature, underlining the efficacy and benefits of VRI technology. For instance, Yabe (2020) highlighted that healthcare providers reported enhanced communication with patients and greater comfort for both parties when utilizing VRI technology. Similarly, Marshall et al. (2019) observed that the introduction of VRI in an acute care facility underscores the critical role of accessible language services. They particularly noted an uptick in VRI usage within SCH clinics that were previously underserved by in-person interpreting options. These findings align closely with the outcomes observed in this project, further affirming the value of VRI technology as a significant tool for improving patient-provider interactions, especially in linguistically diverse healthcare settings. This congruence with the broader body of evidence underscores the relevance and potential impact of our quality improvement efforts in enhancing communication and care delivery in multilingual environments.

Recommendations

VRI service has no geographical constraints and access to interpreters anywhere and anytime (Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). However, some providers reported a negative experience using the VRI that decreased provider-patient relationships, such as a lack of familiarity with the technology, connectivity, internet outages, equipment failure, and message misunderstanding (Kushalnagar et al., 2019; Yabe, 2020). This decreased satisfaction with VRI services suggests that increased education among healthcare providers is warranted.

Implications

A provider needs to understand their role as an agent of change. One way to demonstrate provider acceptance of this role is to recognize that concepts are communicated through language (AONE, 2015). Suppose the patient who is Deaf/HH cannot understand the provider. In that case, the provider failed to communicate to change the patient's quality of life (physical, emotional, and spiritual). VRI is an assistive technology breakthrough that will enhance provider and patient communication and improve the Deaf/HH urgent care experience.

The adoption of VRI technology represents a significant advance in assistive technologies, offering a practical solution to enhance the interaction between providers and patients. This innovation not only facilitates clearer communication but also significantly reduces the risk of misunderstandings, thereby improving the overall healthcare experience for Deaf/HH individuals. For healthcare educators and stakeholders, it is imperative to recognize the importance of integrating VRI into healthcare settings and to promote its usage as part of a broader strategy to ensure equitable care for all patients, regardless of hearing ability. This approach underscores the necessity of adapting healthcare practices to meet the diverse needs of the patient population, ultimately leading to more inclusive and effective care delivery.

Limitations

The project was limited to sample size. Furthermore, due to time constraints, implementation of VRI was not available, which would have consisted of vetting vendors, educating providers and staff, improving internet connectivity and bandwidth, and purchasing video monitor devices. These limitations affect the generalizability of the results and the implementation of the service. A total of 14 participants finished both pre- and post-surveys. However, if participants did not answer all questions, the total may decrease to 12 if two participants missed a question or to 13 if only one participant missed a question.

Conclusion

The days of ineffective communication are a foregone conclusion, especially in today's multisystem technological communication advancements. Language barriers place the Deaf/HH at a disadvantage when seeking healthcare. Relying on lip-reading and note-writing is a poor option for communication. Effective communication is the global gold standard of relationships. Nurse leaders explore opportunities to advocate for their patients while advancing their practice. Therefore, healthcare organizations must promote clinical EBP in organizational decision-making by involving nursing in decisions that affect practice while promoting patient-centered care. VRI technology will improve the healthcare of the Deaf/HH in clinical practice. In the absence of a professional ASL interpreter, VRI is the preferred choice for a patient who is Deaf/HH.

References

- Abou-Abdallah, M., & Lamyman, A. (2021). Exploring communication difficulties with deaf patients. *Clinical Medicine*, 21(4), e380–e383. <https://doi.org/10.7861/clinmed.2021-0111>
- American Association of Colleges of Nursing. (n.d.). *Communication concepts*. <https://www.aacnnursing.org/essentials/tool-kit/domainsconcepts/communication#:~:text=Communication%2C%20informed%20by%20nursing%20and,through%20a%20variety%20of%20mechanisms>
- American Association of Critical-Care Nurses. (2019, April 24). *A conversation with Florence Nightingale*. <https://www.aacn.org/nursing-excellence/nurse-stories/a-conversation-with-florence-nightingale>
- American Organization of Nurse Executives. (2015). *Nurse executive competencies*. <https://www.aonl.org/sites/default/files/aone/nec.pdf>
- Babenko, O., Koppula, S., Daniels, L., Nadon, L., & Daniels, V. (2017). Lifelong learning along the education and career continuum: Meta-analysis of studies in health professions. *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism*, 5(4), 157–163. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5611424/>
- Bodenmann, P., Singy, P., Kasztura, M., Graells, M., Cantero, O., Morisod, K., Malebranche, M., Smith, P., Beyeler, S., Sebaï, T., & Grazioli, V. S. (2021). Developing and evaluating a capacity-building intervention for healthcare providers to improve communication skills and awareness of hard of hearing and D/deaf populations: Protocol for a participative action research-based study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, Article 615474. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.615474>

- Bonnel, W. E., & Smith, K. V. (2022). *Proposal writing for clinical nursing and DNP projects* (3rd ed.). Springer Publishing Company.
- Broca, P. V., & de Ferreira, M. A. (2018). Nursing team communication in a medical ward. *Brazilian Nursing Journal [Revista Brasileira de Enfermagem]*, 71(3), 951–958.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2017-0208>
- Cambridge Dictionary. (n.d.). *Non-directive*.
<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/non-directive>
- Cornell University. (n.d.). *Disability statistics: Online resource for U.S. disability statistics*.
- Deane, W. H., & Fain, J. A. (2016). Incorporating Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations to promote holistic communication between older adults and nursing students. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 34(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0898010115577975>
- Ebert, D. A., & Heckerling, P. S. (1995). Communication with deaf patients. Knowledge, beliefs, and practices of physicians. *JAMA*, 273(3), 227–229.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1995.03520270061032>
- Fernandes, R. L., de Miranda, N., & Arlando, F. (2016). Analysis of the theory of interpersonal relationships: Nursing care in psychosocial care centers. *Journal of Nursing UFPE*, 10(Suppl 2), 880–886. <https://doi.org/10.5205/reuol.6884-59404-2-SM-1.1002sup201624>
- Flores, G. (2005). The impact of medical interpreter services on the quality of health care: A systematic review. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 62(3), 255–299.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077558705275416>
- Flores, G., Abreu, M., Barone, C. P., Bachur, R., & Lin, H. (2012). Errors of medical interpretation and their potential clinical consequences: A comparison of professional

versus ad hoc versus no interpreters. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 60(5), 545–553.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2012.01.025>

Fossli, J. B., Gulbrandsen, P., Dahl, F. A., Krupat, E., Frankel, R. M., & Finset, A. (2011).

Effectiveness of a short course in clinical communication skills for hospital doctors:

Results of a crossover randomized controlled trial (ISRCTN22153332). *Patient*

Education & Counseling, 84(2), 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2010.08.028>

Gabrielsen, A. K., Karlsen, M. M. W., Falch, A. L., & Stubberud, D.-G. (2016). Communication training course with simulation. *Norwegian Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 11(2), 184–192.

<https://doi.org/10.4220/Sykepleienf.2016.57832>

Gonzalo, A. (2023, July 2). *Hildegard Peplau: Interpersonal relations theory*. Nurseslabs.

<https://nurseslabs.com/hildegard-peplaus-interpersonal-relations-theory/>

Gracia, J. E., Serrano, R. B., & Garrido, J. F. (2019). Medication errors and drug knowledge gaps among critical-care nurses: A mixed multi-method study. *BMC Health Services*

Research, 19(1), Article 640. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-4481-7>

Hagerty, T. A. (2015). *Testing Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations in nursing using data from patient experience surveys center* [Doctoral dissertation, City University of New York]. CUNY Academic Works.

https://academicworks.cuny.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1974&context=gc_etds

Hagerty, T. A., Samuels, W., Norcini-Pala, A., & Gigliotti, E. (2017). Peplau's theory of

interpersonal relations: An alternate factor structure for patient experience data? *Nursing science quarterly*, 30(2), 160–167. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894318417693286>

Helitzer, D. L., LaNoue, M., Wilson, B., de Hernandez, B. U., Warner, T., & Roter, D. (2011). A randomized controlled trial of communication training with primary care providers to

- improve patient-centeredness and health risk communication. *Patient Education & Counseling*, 82(1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2010.01.021>
- Hommel, R. E., Borash, A. I., Hartwig, K., & DeGracia, D. (2018). American sign language interpreters perceptions of barriers to healthcare communication in deaf and hard of hearing patients. *Journal of Community Health*, 43(5), 956–961. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-018-0511-3>
- Hurtig, R. R., Alper, R. M., & Berkowitz, B. (2018). The cost of not addressing the communication barriers faced by hospitalized patients. *Perspectives of the ASHA Special Interest Groups*, 3(12), 99–112. <https://doi.org/10.1044/persp3.SIG12.99>
- Jardien-Baboo, J. S., Rooyen, D., Ricks, E. R., & Jordan, P. (2016). Perceptions of patient-centered care at public hospitals in Nelson Mandela Bay. *Health SA Gesondheid*, 21(1), 397–405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hsag.2016.05.002>
- Karliner, L. S., Jacobs, E. A., Chen, A. H., & Mutha, S. (2007). Do professional interpreters improve clinical care for patients with limited English proficiency? A systematic review of the literature. *Health Services Research*, 42(2), 727–754. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6773.2006.00629.x>
- Kuenburg, A., Fellingner, P., & Fellingner, J. (2016). Health care access among deaf people. *The Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 21(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/env042>
- Kushalnagar, P., Paludneviene, R., & Kushalnagar, R. (2019). Video remote interpreting technology in health care: Cross-sectional study of deaf patients' experiences. *JMIR Rehabilitation and Assistive Technologies*, 6(1), Article e13233. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13233>

- Lefler, L. (2005). The advanced practice nurse's role regarding women's delay in seeking treatment with myocardial infarction. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners, 14*(10), 449–456. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-7599.2002.tb00075.x>
- Levinson, W., Lesser, C. S., & Epstein, R. M. (2010). Developing physician communication skills for patient-centered care. *Health Affairs, 29*(7), 1310–1318. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2009.0450>
- Lin, S. P., Chang, C.-W., Wu, C.-Y., Chin, C.-S., Lin, C.-H., Shiu, S.-I., Chen, Y.-W., Yen, T.-H., Chen, H.-C., Lai, Y.-H., Hou, S.-C., Wu, M.-J., & Chen, H.-H. (2022). The effectiveness of multidisciplinary team huddles in healthcare hospital-based setting. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare, 15*, 2241–2247. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JMDH.S384554>
- Lion, K. C., Brown, J. C., Ebel, B. E., Klein, E. J., Strelitz, B., Gutman, C. K., Hencz, P., Fernandez, J., & Mangione-Smith, R. (2015). Effect of telephone vs video interpretation on parent comprehension, communication, and utilization in the pediatric emergency department: A randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Pediatrics, 169*(12), 1117–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2015.2630>
- Marquete, V. F., Teston, E. F., de Souza, R. R., de Lima Vieira, V. C., Fischer, M. M. J. B., & Marcon, S. S. (2019). Care challenges for deaf people experienced by hearing family members: An exploratory study. *Online Brazilian Journal of Nursing, 18*(3), Article e20196212. <http://www.objnursing.uff.br/index.php/nursing/article/view/6212/html>
- Marshall, L. C., Zaki, A., Duarte, M., Nicolas, A., Roan, J., Colby, A. F., Noyes, A. L., & Flores, G. (2019). Promoting effective communication with limited English proficient families: Implementation of video remote interpreting as part of a comprehensive language

- services program in a children's hospital. *Joint Commission Journal on Quality & Patient Safety*, 45(7), 509-516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjq.2019.04.001>
- McKee, M. M., Barnett, S. L., Block, R. C., & Pearson, T. A. (2011). Impact of communication on preventive services among deaf American sign language users. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 41(1), 75–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2011.03.004>
- Mena Lora, A. J., Ali, M., Krill, C., Spencer, S., Takhsh, E., & Bleasdale, S. C. (2020). Impact of a hospital-wide huddle on device utilisation and infection rates: A community hospital's journey to zero. *Journal of Infection Prevention*, 21(6), 228–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1757177420939239>
- Morisod, K., Malebranche, M., Marti, J., Spycher, J., Grazioli, V. S., & Bodenmann, P. (2022). Interventions aimed at improving healthcare and health education equity for adult d/Deaf patients: A systematic review. *European Journal of Public Health*, 32(4), 548–556. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac056>
- Napier, J., Lloyd, K., Skinner, R., Turner, G., & Wheatley, M. (2018). Using video technology to engage deaf sign language users in survey research: An example from the Insign project. *The International Journal of Translation & Interpreting Research*, 10(2), 101-121. <http://www.trans-int.org/index.php/transint/article/view/768>
- National Collaborating Centre for Methods and Tools. (n.d.). *Stetler model of evidence-based practice*. <https://www.nccmt.ca/knowledge-repositories/search/83>
- Orrie, S., & Motsahi, T. (2018). Challenges experienced by healthcare workers in managing patients with hearing impairment at a primary health care setting: A descriptive case study. *South African Family Practice*, 60(6), 207–211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20786190.2018.1507566>

- Penckofer, S., Byrn, M., Mumby, P., & Ferrans, C. E. (2011). Improving subject recruitment, retention, and participation in research through Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 24(2), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894318411399454>
- Peplau, H. E. (1991). *Interpersonal relations in nursing: A conceptual frame of reference for psychodynamic nursing*. Springer
- Pickens, B. (2021). Communicating with the American sign language user in the emergency department. *Journal of Emergency Nursing*, 47(1), 16-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2020.09.004>
- Pimentel, C. B., Snow, A. L., Carnes, S. L., Shah, N. R., Loup, J. R., Vallejo-Luces, T. M., Madrigal, C., & Hartmann, C. W. (2021). Huddles and their effectiveness at the frontlines of clinical care: A scoping review. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 36(9), 2772–2783. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-021-06632-9>
- Reeves, D., & Kokoruwe, B. (2005). Communication and communication support in primary care: A survey of deaf patients. *Audiological Medicine*, 3(2), 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16513860510033747>
- Riedl, D., & Schüßler, G. (2017). The influence of doctor-patient communication on health outcomes: A systematic review. *Journal of Psychosomatic Medicine and Psychotherapy [Zeitschrift für Psychosomatische Medizin und Psychotherapie]*, 63(2), 131-150. <https://doi.org/10.13109/zptm.2017.63.2.131>
- Robinson, J. H., Callister, L. C., Berry, J. A., & Dearing, K. A. (2008). Patient-centered care and adherence: Definitions and applications to improve outcomes. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*, 20(12), 600–607. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-7599.2008.00360.x>

- Rogers, C. R., Lyon, H. C., Jr., & Tausch, R. (2014). *On becoming an effective teacher: Person-centered teaching, psychology, philosophy, and dialogues with Carl R Rogers and Harold Lyon*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Romp, C. R., & Kiehl, E. (2009). Applying the Stetler model of research utilization in staff development: Revitalizing a preceptor program. *Journal for Nurses in Staff Development*, 25(6), 278–286. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0b013e3181c2654a>
- Scheier, D. B. (2009). Barriers to health care for people with hearing loss: A review of the literature. *The Journal of the New York State Nurses' Association*, 40(1), 4–10.
- Schoenborn, C. A., & Heyman, K. (2008, May). *Health disparities among adults with hearing loss: United States, 2000–2006*. National Center for Health Statistics. <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/hestat/hearing00-06/hearing00-06.pdf>
- Senn, J. F. (2013). Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations: Application in emergency and rural nursing. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 26(1), 31–35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894318412466744>
- Sirch, L., Salvador, L., & Palese, A. (2017). Communication difficulties experienced by deaf male patients during their in-hospital stay: Findings from a qualitative descriptive study. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 31(2), 368–377. <https://doi.org/10.1111/scs.12356>
- Stetler, C. B. (2001). Updating the Stetler model of research utilization to facilitate evidence-based practice. *Nursing Outlook*, 49(6), 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1067/mno.2001.120517>
- U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division. (2009, June 15). *Americans with disabilities act of 1990, as amended*. <https://www.ada.gov/pubs/adastatute08.htm>

- U.S. Department of Justice Civil Rights Division. (2020, February 28). *ADA requirements: Effective communication*. <https://www.ada.gov/resources/effective-communication/>
- Villaseñor, S., & Krouse, H. J. (2016). Can the use of urgent care clinics improve access to care without undermining continuity in primary care? *Journal of the American Association of Nurse Practitioners*, 28(6), 335–341. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2327-6924.12314>
- Walker, L. O., & Avant, K. C. (2018). *Strategies for theory construction in nursing* (6th ed.). Pearson.
- Wasaya, F., Shah, Q., Shaheen, A., & Carroll, K. (2021). Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations: A case study. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 34(4), 368–371. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08943184211031573>
- White, K. M. (2019). Chapter one: Evidence-based practice and its implementation in healthcare. In K. White, S. Dudley-Brown, & M. Terhaar (Eds.), *Translation of evidence into nursing and healthcare* (3rd ed., pp. 3-25). Springer. <https://connect.springerpub.com/content/book/978-0-8261-4737-0/part/part01/chapter/ch01>
- Winkel, A. F., Yingling, S., Jones, A.-A., & Nicholson, J. (2017). Reflection as a learning tool in graduate medical education: A systematic review. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 9(4), 430–439. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-D-16-00500.1>
- World Health Organization. (2024, February 2). *Deafness and hearing loss*. <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/deafness-and-hearing-loss>
- Yabe, M. (2020). Healthcare providers' and deaf patients' interpreting preferences for critical care and non-critical care: Video remote interpreting. *Disability and Health Journal*, 13(2), Article 100870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2019.100870>

Appendix A

Major Concepts of Peplau's Theory of Interpersonal Relationships

Figure A1

Peplau's Framework: Major Concepts

Note. From “Testing Peplau's Theory of Interpersonal Relations in Nursing Using Data From Patient Experience Surveys Center,” by T. A. Hagerty, 2015, CUNY Academic Works.

https://academicworks.cuny.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1974&context=gc_etds

Copyright 2015 by City University of New York.

Appendix B

Peplau's Theory of Interpersonal Relationships

Figure B1

Peplau's Theory of Interpersonal Relationships

Note. From “Hildegard Peplau: Interpersonal Relations Theory,” by A. Gonzalo, 2023

(<https://nurseslabs.com/hildegard-peplaus-interpersonal-relations-theory/>). Copyright 2023 by

Nurseslabs.

Appendix C

Stetler Model of Research Utilization

Figure C1

Stetler Model of Research Utilization to Facilitate Evidence-Based Practice

Note. r, r, r, resources, readiness, and risk factors. From "Updating the Stetler Model of Research Utilization to Facilitate Evidence-Based Practice," by C. B. Stetler, 2001, *Nursing Outlook*, 49(6), p. 276 (<https://doi.org/10.1067/mno.2001.120517>). Copyright 2001 by Elsevier.

Appendix D
IRB Approval Letter

Office Memorandum

DATE:	December 11, 2023
TO:	Ayman Tailakh, Ph.D
FROM:	LaTreshia Scott
PROJECT TITLE:	[2099415-1] A More Effective Way to Communicate With the Deaf Seeking Healthcare in Urgent Care
REFERENCE #:	23-70X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	October 27, 2023
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category # 2(i), 2(ii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact LaTreshia Scott. It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

Appendix E

Institutional Approval Letter

INSTITUTIONAL APPROVAL LETTER

Date: 04/03/2023

This letter is to show that _____ the CEO _____ give permission to Kevin Foster (project lead) to conduct the project titled, A More Effective Way to Communicate with the Deaf Seeking Healthcare in the Urgent Care at the following.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from _____ and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect data from the Clinical Provider Survey pre-and post-test.
- (2) conduct necessary interactions with providers relevant to (a) the Clinical Provider Survey pre-and post-test, (b) Provider Protocol for Improving Communication with the Deaf/HH using video remote interpreter (VRI), and (c) Provider Interpersonal Communication and Self-Reflection Awareness Instrument.
- (3) distribute Clinical Provider Survey pre-and post-test using the providers' email

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations. If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Sincerely,
Kevin Foster MSN, NP, PA

Signature:

Name:

Title:

Contact Information:

Signature:

Name:

Title:

Contact Information:

Appendix F
Pre-Clinical Survey

1. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
 - other
2. What license do you practice under?
 - PA
 - NP
 - DO
 - MD
3. How many years of health care experience do you have?
 - 1-5
 - 6-10
 - 11-15
 - 16-20
 - More than 20
4. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - Bachelor's
 - Master's
 - Doctoral
 - Doctor of osteopathic
 - Medical doctor
5. Which languages are you fluent in? (Check all that apply)
 - American Sign Language (ASL)
 - Spanish
 - Armenian
 - English
 - Chinese (Cantonese)
 - Chinese (Mandarin)
 - Korean
 - Other
6. What is your age?
 - 20–25
 - 26–30
 - 31–35
 - 36–40
 - 41–45
 - 46–50
 - 51–55
 - 56–60
 - Older than 60 years
7. How comfortable do you feel rendering care for a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very much so

8. How often do you discuss language barriers among providers when considering a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
9. How confident do you feel in treating a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
10. How often do you treat a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
11. How often do you educate a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
12. Are the Deaf who seek urgent care accompanied by a hearing family member or friend?
 - Yes
 - No
13. Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily female?
 - Yes
 - No
14. Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily male?
 - Yes
 - No
15. Do the Deaf who seek urgent care read lips?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
16. Have you used video remote interpreter (VRI) technology?
 - Yes
 - No
17. Do you think your confidence level treating the Deaf or hard of hearing will increase after using video remote interpreter (VRI) technology?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Somewhat
 - Mostly
 - Very Much
18. How often do you engage in self-reflection as a provider in your practice?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly

- Somewhat
- Mostly
- Very Much

19. How often do you utilize non-directive listening?

- Not at all
- Slightly
- Somewhat
- Mostly
- Very Much

20. How often do you reflect on your professional calling/role as an agent of change?

- Not at all
- Slightly
- Somewhat
- Mostly
- Very Much

Appendix G

Post-Clinical Post Survey

1. Do you think gender has a role in how you treat and educate persons who are Deaf and hard of hearing?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
2. Do you believe your license played a role in how you answered the pre-survey?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
3. Do you believe your years of practice determined your ability to treat persons who are Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
4. Do you think your level of education helps you better understand the communication disparities faced by the persons who are Deaf or hard of hearing seeking urgent care?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
5. Do you think understanding more than one language will help you better serve the persons who are Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
6. Do you think your age plays a role in treating persons who are Deaf or hard of hearing?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
7. After completing the pre-survey and its components, do you feel better equipped to communicate and treat people who are Deaf or hard of hearing in urgent care?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
8. Will you discuss language barriers more often now that you have participated in this survey?
 - Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree

- Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
9. Has your confidence level improved after taking part in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
10. Do you think you will treat more patients who are Deaf and hard of hearing after taking part in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
11. Do you think you are better equipped to educate patients who are Deaf and hard of hearing after participating in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
12. After taking part in this survey, do you believe there are significant disparities for the person who is Deaf or hard of hearing seeking treatment in urgent care?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
13. Do you think you can make a difference in the life of the Deaf or hard-of-hearing patient seeking urgent care?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
14. Do you believe you are better equipped to help guide the person who is Deaf or hard of hearing through their healthcare challenges in urgent care?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
15. After taking part in this survey, do you believe video remote interpreting services (VRI) are a better communication option for the Deaf and hard of hearing seeking urgent care than lip reading or written notes?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
16. Would you request a video remote interpreting service (VRI) through your urgent care employer after participating in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree

- Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
17. Do you think your confidence level has improved regarding using video remote interpreting (VRI) service in urgent care after taking part in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
18. Will you self-reflect more often after participating in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
19. Will your non-directive listening increase and improve after participating in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
20. Do you better understand your role as an agent of change after taking part in this survey?
- Strongly disagreed
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree

Appendix H

Standard Operations Protocol

Table H1*Protocol*

Section	Provider Action	Rationale
Primary Concerns	Ensure high-quality audio/video over a dedicated high-speed wide bandwidth or wireless connection with video image without pause in communication, choppiness, or blurriness.	Ensure quality communication with an ASL interpreter absent an in-person ASL interpreter.
Video Size and Image	Provide a large, clear image of both the ASL interpreters face, hands, arms as well as the patient who is Deaf/HH.	ASL is a visual language using facial expressions, hands, fingers, and arm gestures to communicate feelings, thoughts, questions, concerns, and ideas.
VRI Placement	Place VRI at a comfortable (patient preference) distance in front of the patient who is Deaf/HH.	Empowering patient to become active in the decision making regarding their care.
Clear Audio/Voice Transmission	Ensure audio is working appropriately and is non-obstructed for the clarity of dialogue.	The hearing provider must be able to communicate with the ASL interpreter.
Staff Training	To ensure quick and proper VRI setup operation, staff must be adequately trained.	Saves time and demonstrates providers/staff knowledge and professionalism.
Deaf Communication 101	Turning off and on lights.	This will most often capture the attention of the Deaf.
Deaf Communication 101	Face the patient making eye contact.	Communication respect and enhances interpreting facial expressions.
Deaf Communication 101	Remove face mask.	Many Deaf read lips and facial expressions.
Deaf Communication 101	Don't overexaggerate facial expressions.	Exaggerative facial expressions may lead to miss communication.
Deaf Communication 101	Ask patient their preferred way to communicate.	Some Deaf prefer text, email, VRI, in-person interpreter, lip reading, and writing with a pen and paper.
Deaf Communication 101	Use visual aids.	Visual aids improve communication.

Appendix I

Provider Interpersonal Communication/Self-Reflection/Awareness Instrument

Table I1

Provider Interpersonal Communication/Self-Reflection/Awareness Instrument

Section	Provider Action	Rationale
Primary Concerns	The provider must be able to interpret the patient's primary concern/need/values, an act developed by keen observation through self-reflection, training, and experience.	Ensure the patient concerns/needs are met.
Non-Directive Listening	Learning non-directive techniques (i.e., pause, body language, summarizing/reflecting feelings).	Tools to help illuminate words/thoughts without obviously stating it.
Resource Person	The provider must be comfortable as a resource person answering specific questions related to a more significant problem and know how to research relevant resources.	Having up to date and informative answers for all patients.
Professional Calling/Role	The provider must understand their professional calling/role as a leader, educator, and agent of change achieved through life-long learning.	Help guide the patient through their healthcare challenges.

Appendix J
Steps for VRI Implementation

Turn on the tablet designated for the use of VRI.

1. Go to the online meeting link associated with the VRI portal account.
2. Connect with a qualified professional ASL interpreter.
3. Once connected, place the tablet in front of the patient who is Deaf/HH.
4. The interpreter will interpret the Deaf/HH and hearing communications during the call to answer all questions and concerns by the Deaf/HH and provider regarding informed consent, allergy history, past medical history, past surgical history, diagnosis, treatment plans, patient desires, teaching, medications, follow up plans, discharge instructions and end of visit survey.
5. Once the call is complete, log off.

Appendix K

TLC

Figure K1

Turn on Language to Communicate Acronym

Appendix L

Pre-and Post-Survey Response

Figure L1

Note. The graph reflects providers' pre- and post-survey responses to seven questions. One, providers' confidence in treating the Deaf/HH. Two, providers' comfort in treating the Deaf/HH. Three, providers' see themselves as change agents. Four, providers discuss language barriers. Five, providers' eagerness to treat the Deaf/HH; six, providers' use of VRI; and seven, providers' non-directive listening.

Appendix M
Results Tables

Table M1*Demographic Characteristics of Providers*

Variable	Testing time	
	Pretest	Posttest
Gender		
Female	6 (46.15%)	6 (46.15%)
Male	7 (53.85%)	7 (53.85%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	13 (100.00%)
License practice		
PA	11 (84.62%)	11 (84.62%)
NP	2 (15.38%)	2 (15.38%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	13 (100.00%)
Years health experience		
6-10	2 (15.38%)	2 (16.67%)
11-15	1 (7.69%)	1 (8.33%)
16-20	1 (7.69%)	1 (8.33%)
more than 20	9 (69.23%)	8 (66.67%)
Total	13 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)
Highest education		
Bachelor's	4 (33.33%)	4 (33.33%)
Master's	7 (58.33%)	7 (58.33%)
Doctoral	1 (8.33%)	1 (8.33%)
Total	12 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)
Fluent languages		
English	9 (81.82%)	9 (75.00%)
Armenian	1 (9.09%)	2 (16.67%)
Other	1 (9.09%)	1 (8.33%)
Total	11 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not sum to 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.

Table M2*Baseline Provider Perspectives, Practices, and Deaf/HH Demographics*

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
How comfortable do you feel rendering care for a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	5	38.46
Somewhat	2	15.38
Mostly	2	15.38
Very Much	4	30.77
How often do you discuss language barriers among providers when considering a patient who is Deaf or hard of hearing?		
Not at all	2	15.38
Slightly	7	53.85
Somewhat	3	23.08
Mostly	1	7.69
How confident do you feel in treating a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	3	23.08
Somewhat	2	15.38
Mostly	2	15.38
Very Much	6	46.15
How often do you treat a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Slightly	10	76.92
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	1	7.69
How often do you educate a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Not at all	2	15.38
Slightly	8	61.54
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	1	7.69
Very Much	1	7.69
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care accompanied by a hearing family member or friend?		
Yes	12	92.31

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily female?		
Yes	5	38.46
Are the Deaf who seek urgent care primarily male?		
Yes	3	23.08
Do the Deaf who seek urgent care read lips?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Slightly	2	15.38
Somewhat	1	7.69
Mostly	8	61.54
Very Much	1	7.69
Have you used video remote interpreter VRI technology?		
Yes	3	23.08

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Table M3

Provider Confidence and Reflective Practices

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Do you think your confidence level treating the Deaf or hard-of-hearing will increase after using video remote interpreter VRI technology?		
Somewhat	2	15.38
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	3	23.08
Very Much	7	53.85
How often do you engage in self-reflection as a provider in your practice?		
Somewhat	4	30.77
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	4	30.77
Very Much	4	30.77
How often do you utilize non-directive listening?		
Not at all	1	7.69
Somewhat	5	38.46

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Slightly	3	23.08
Mostly	1	7.69
Very Much	3	23.08
How often do you reflect on your professional calling/role as an agent of change?		
Somewhat	6	46.15
Slightly	1	7.69
Mostly	3	23.08
Very Much	3	23.08

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not sum to 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.

Table M4

Impact of VRI Training Video on Healthcare Providers' Confidence and Practices with Deaf/HH

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
After watching the VRI Video, how comfortable do you feel rendering care for a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	5	35.71
Very Much	6	42.86
After watching the VRI Video, will you discuss language barriers among providers when considering a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing?		
Slightly	2	14.29
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
Has your confidence level in treating a patient who is Deaf or hard-of-hearing improved after watching the video?		
Not at all	1	7.14
Slightly	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
Do you think you will treat more patients who are Deaf and hard-of-hearing after watching the video?		
Slightly	3	21.43
Somewhat	3	21.43
Mostly	2	14.29
Very Much	6	42.86
Do you think you are better equipped to educate patients who are Deaf and hard-of-hearing after watching the video?		
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	4	28.57
Very Much	8	57.14
Will you self-reflect more often after watching the video?		
Somewhat	5	35.71
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	6	42.86
Will your non-directive listening increase after watching this video?		
Somewhat	3	21.43
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	8	57.14
After viewing this video, do you have a clearer insight into your professional mission as an advocate for positive change?		
Somewhat	4	28.57
Mostly	5	35.71
Very Much	5	35.71
After watching the video, do you believe that your education as an NP, PA, MD, or DO aids in treating Deaf or hard-of-hearing patients?"		
Somewhat	4	28.57
Mostly	3	21.43
Very Much	7	50.00
After watching the video, do you feel that your experience equips you to effectively use VRI technology in treating Deaf or hard-of-hearing patients?		

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Not at all	1	7.14
Somewhat	2	14.29
Mostly	4	28.57
Very Much	7	50.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%. Any answer choices not selected by participants (i.e., receiving a count of 0) were excluded from the table.